

Performance and kinetics of anoxic biotrickling filtration for hydrogen sulfide removal

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Abstract

Removal of hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) from gaseous effluents constitutes a critical strategy for mitigating environmental impacts, given the physicochemical and toxicological properties of this chemical species [e.g., [1]]. H_2S is highly toxic to living organisms, causing deleterious effects on respiratory and nervous systems upon exposure to concentrations above biological tolerance thresholds [4]. Conventional desulfurization technologies are primarily based on aerobic processes, which suffer from high energy demands due to oxygenation requirements. In this context, anoxic biological systems emerge as a sustainable alternative, providing efficient removal with lower energy input. There remains a significant scientific gap in understanding the mechanisms of H_2S removal in anoxic reactors, in contrast to the well-established knowledge on aerobic systems [2]. The present study aims to simulate and calibrate kinetic models for hydrogen sulfide removal in an innovative anoxic bioreactor configuration. The proposed system is characterized by a fixed bed with biofilm-immobilized microorganisms, operating under a steady liquid-phase regime and gas flow in counter-current mode. The simulation seeks to deepen understanding of the processes involved, offering a systematic approach to optimizing removal efficiency and operational sustainability. Kinetic models were derived from mass balance assumptions, considering the following hypotheses: (i) the reactor is tubular with flow approximating plug-flow behavior; (ii) flow regime is steady; (iii) the system is at steady state; (iv) fluid flow is incompressible. Under these assumptions, the reaction rate can be expressed as: $r = -\frac{dC}{dt} = k \cdot C^n$, where k represents the reaction rate constant, C is pollutant concentration, and n is reaction order. To evaluate the fit between simulation predictions and experimental data, two criteria were employed: the coefficient of determination (R^2) and mean squared error (MSE). Additionally, Michaelis–Menten kinetics were applied to determine the reaction's kinetic order, described by: $\frac{dC}{dt} = \frac{K_{max} \cdot C}{K_s + C}$, where C denotes pollutant concentration in the liquid phase, K_{max} is the maximum degradation rate, and K_s is the half-saturation constant. Results analysis included scenario simulations to identify kinetic parameters for zero-, first-, and second-order kinetics, and thereby assess H_2S removal efficiencies. For simulations, ten datasets were used, 70% for calibration and 30% for validation. Preliminary results (Table 1) from calibration simulations indicate behavior consistent with first-order kinetics: removal rate is proportional to H_2S concentration. Experimental data literature [3] were used to simulate different reaction orders and calibrate the models using Python (v.3.10.4) scripts within a VS Code development environment. The results indicate that the first-order kinetics model without diffusion limitation provided a good fit to the experimental data around concentrations of 50 mg/L. This behavior aligns with a system operating well below saturation conditions. This conclusion is reinforced by Michaelis–Menten analysis, which showed

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a removal rate of $13.6 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, representing only 22% of the theoretical maximum rate of $62.0 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. The half-saturation constant (K_m) = 177.7 mg/L indicates that, under these conditions, the system is operating well below the K_m threshold. Moreover, the derivative of the Michaelis–Menten equation in this regime implies an apparent rate constant of approximately 0.349 h^{-1} , which is on the same order of magnitude as the slope obtained from the first-order model, further confirming consistency between the two modeling approaches. Therefore, preliminary findings suggest that within the current operating concentration range, hydrogen sulfide removal kinetics approximate first-order behavior, validating the model's effective fit. However, because the system may exhibit nonlinear kinetics at other concentration ranges, further experimental studies are recommended, extending the tested concentration range. This would allow more precise evaluation of transitions between kinetic regimes and assessment of whether the first-order simplification remains valid under varied operational conditions.

#	Model	Calibration		Equation
		R ²	MSE	
1	Zero-order kinetics without diffusion limitation	0.9992	1.7×10^{-1}	$-0.468 \cdot \theta + 49.7 = Ct$
2	First-order kinetics without diffusion limitation	0.9955	5.1×10^{-4}	$-0.014 \cdot \theta + 3.94 = \ln[C]$
3	Second-order kinetics without diffusion limitation	0.9754	2.9×10^{-6}	$0.00046 \cdot \theta + 0.018 = 1/Ct$
4	Zero-order kinetics with diffusion limitation	0.9999	4.3×10^{-13}	$-1.121 \times 10^{-5} \cdot \theta + 0.069 = Ct$
5	Michaelis-Menten	0.9673	1.1×10^{-1}	V _{max} : $62.0 \text{ mg/L}\cdot\text{h}$; K _m : 177.7 mg/L r: $13 \text{ mg/L}\cdot\text{h}$ k _{ap} = 0.349 h^{-1}

Table 1. Results of the Calibration Step for the Simulation of Hydrogen Sulfide Removal Kinetics

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